

KWAME NKRUMAH UNIVERISTY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, KUMASI

COLLEGE OF SCIENCE

DEPARTMENT OF THEORETICAL AND APPLIED BIOLOGY

**ASSESSMENT OF THE WATER QUALITY AT THE TRADITIONAL
HALLS OF RESIDENCE AT THE KNUST CAMPUS, KUMASI**

**A THESIS SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF THEORETICAL AND APPLIED
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BACHELOR OF SCIENCE DEGREE IN BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES**

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DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to the LORD Almighty for keeping us safely throughout our stay in school and to our parents Mr. Dan N. Asihene and Mr. and Mrs. Quarcoo for their enormous and unending support in this sector of our education.

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ABSTRACT

Water is essential for every organism's upkeep. Without water, life becomes unbearable as most of our physiological functioning and daily activities are dependent on it hence affecting us. Water is one of the abundant resource on the earth but the quality aspects raises much concern to its use. The study was done to assess the physicochemical and microbial quality of water supplied to students and workers on KNUST campus, Kumasi, from sample the various halls of residence namely; Africa, Unity, Republic, Queen Elizabeth, Independence and University hall with sample code C01, C02, C03, C04, C05, C06. Analysis conducted indicated good physicochemical levels of the parameters with pH ranging from 6.60 - 6.81, electrical conductivity levels from 152179($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), total alkalinity recorded was between 35 - 51mg/L. Fluoride concentration ranged between 0.20 – 0.29mg/L, chloride levels recorded ranged from 0.29 – 0.37mg/L and temperature values ranged from 23.1 – 23.7 °C. Microbial quality were high with total coliform ranging from 2.53×10^6 MPN/100ml - 4.65×10^5 MPN/100ml and fecal coliform ranging between 87×10^5 MPN/100ml - 4.00×10^4 MPN/100ml. The water samples were also tested for the presence of Enterococci which recorded values of 1.05×10^6 CFU/mL - 5.51×10^4 CFU/mL with *Escherichia coli* present in sample obtained from site C02. The underground water supplied to the various halls (sampled sites) in KNUST were physico-chemically good but bacteriologically unfit for consumption and use. It is therefore recommended that the storage containers and distribution systems are cleaned regularly and water is also treated timely to prevent further contamination and health related issues to end users; spillage or leakage of the various sewage pipe lines should also be checked.

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Water has always been a daily necessity for all living things. Water is essential for life and human health, economic development, food security, alleviating poverty reduction and sustainable ecological functions (Connor, 2015). Without water, life is as unbearable as one can imagine and can lead to the extinction of every form of life on earth. World Meteorological Organization agrees without doubt that water is highly essential for human survival (WMO, 2012). However, over 844 million people on the earth have no access to good quality drinking water and about 2.3 billion people still lack access to adequate sanitation facilities (WHO and UNICEF, 2017). Although water-related diseases have largely been eliminated in wealthier nations, they remain a major concern in much of the developing world (Gleick, 2002), and these problems are one of the manifestations of poverty in the developing countries (Chalchisa *et al.*, 2017). The most valuable commodity in the world today, and likely to remain so for much of this century, is not oil or natural gas or even some type of renewable energy but water, clean, safe, fresh water (Larry, 2013). Natural water has populated a wide area of the earth surface but the quality aspect raises many concerns with regards to its uses.

1.2 Use and benefits of water

Water has many beneficial uses to man aside drinking thus serving as a needful resource. It serves as a source of transportation, thus, ships, canoes, boats and other machineries are used to convey humans and animals from one area to the other across a water body. Transportation of goods and

resources from other countries can also be conveyed across water bodies like the sea, lakes and rivers. Moreover, water serves as a source of food for man and other animals. Algae, which is plant-like, coupled with aquatic animals like fishes provide man with food. Industries also use water in most of their activities, in processing, and making products. In agriculture, water is needed to irrigate the crops and farm plantings. In addition, water is used for recreational and frolic activities such as swimming, building aquarium and for scientific studies or purpose.

The human body is said to consist of volumes of water more than solids. This adds to the reason for which water is of an essence to man. A number of physiological processes occurring in humans make use of water, therefore, humans are advised to take in a lot of water to conserve and maintain these physiological mechanisms (Wang *et al.*, 2017). Contaminated water can cause many harm to the human body affecting some of these physiological processes including digestion, excretion, growth and many others (Pal *et al.*, 2018). Hence the need for drinking safe and quality water.

1.3 Sources of water

Water is obtained from two major natural sources; superficial water such as fresh water lakes, streams and ground water from drills, borehole and wells (Gichuki and Gichumbi, 2012). Surface water with its increasing contamination and pollution cannot meet the needs of the increasing populace, thus, has led to groundwater use as an alternative source. It therefore becomes necessary to access the groundwater quality and levels to ensure effective management.

1.4 Quality and Safe water

Safe water refers to any potable water that is free from microbes or chemical contaminants and will not harm the user when taken in or used for other purposes. There are many ways contaminant can get into water rendering it unsafe but making sure the water is free from pathogens which may cause harm to the consumer is of priority. Assessment of the quality of water is the evaluation of the physicochemical and biological constituents of water in relation to natural quality, human effects and intended uses, particularly uses which may affect the health and wellbeing of humans, animals or aquatic systems (Aazami *et al.*, 2015).

1.5 Microorganism in relation to water

Microorganisms are said to be ubiquitous and thus found almost everywhere, with water inclusive. These microorganisms are said to be pathogenic when they pose danger or harm to man and animals. Examples of pathogens include viruses, bacteria, fungi and parasites. It is known that most of the diseases caused by using contaminated water are spread by these harmful microorganisms (WHO and UNICEF, 2018). Examples of such disease are cholera, typhoid, paratyphoid, cryptosporidiosis etc. Fecal organisms have been deemed as popular organisms to monitor in water especially groundwater because of its ability to be present in high numbers in the feces of humans and animals, and also because of its ability to be detected (Rodrigues and Cunha, 2017). Underground drainage systems, waste water and materials, wash-downs of agriculture manures and chemicals into the ground are a major source of contamination for most underground waters. Current guidelines recommend the use of *Escherichia coli* or thermo-tolerant (“fecal”) coliforms are used as indicators of fecal contamination of drinking water. Despite their broad use as measures of water quality, there remain limited evidence for an association between *Escherichia*

coli or thermo-tolerant coliform and diarrheal illness: a previous review found no evidence for a link between diarrhea and these indicators in household drinking water (Gruber *et al.*, 2014). Ministry of Water Resources, Works and Housing of Government of Ghana highlights examples of hazardous events and their potential sources of contamination of water of which “treatment” is one of the events. Monitoring the quality of water in the distribution systems which are supplied to end users is important in delivering quality and safe water to consumers (MWRWH, 2015). Growth of biofilms and contamination can occur through tanks, reservoirs and pipes, etc. The sources of contamination may include, disposal of waste materials (human and inappropriate treatment plans), use of unapproved or contaminated treatment chemicals, equipment malfunctions, aged pipes and many others.

1.6 Problem Statement

The water received from the halls serve other purpose aside drinking such as cleaning, washing, coking etc. Skin infections and sore throat are the major complaints received from the students on the usage of the water. Due to the enclosed nature of the poly-tanks, reservoirs and pipe lines through which the underground water and surface water in our various halls are channeled, most students and other work personnel in the halls of residence may perceive that the water might be one of the best quality water sources for consumption. Lack of quality water supply, irregular treatment plans and cleaning of the tanks and lack of the frequent change of pipe lines can pose many health risks to the end users. Notwithstanding the increasing number of examples of declining groundwater conditions, knowledge on the status of groundwater resources is scattered and there is a lack of solid data (Wijnen *et al.*, 2012). The question still remains, “Should we wait for complaints before quality water is supplied?”

1.7 Justification

Concerns of quality water in some instances may arise from the public complaints about the taste, color, sediments present, organisms seen or odor. The chemical constituents are not of notable essence as an evidence of unsafe water since they are not seen. We do not need to wait for complains and observations of some physical parameters like color, odor, taste etc. before quality water is made available for use and consumption. Students and work personnel who drink and use the water from the halls stand a risk of ingesting harmful chemicals and microbes which may be as a results of the untimely cleaning of reservoirs, poly-tanks, pipelines etc.

This project therefore seeks assess the microbial and physicochemical quality of the groundwater supplied at the various halls of residence in Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology (KNUST) campus.

1.8 Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is to assess the microbial and physicochemical quality of water at the various halls of residence in the KNUST campus.

1.8.1 Specific Objective of the Study

This study specifically seeks to:

1. Determine some physicochemical parameters including pH, temperature, electrical conductivity, alkalinity, chloride and fluoride of the underground water in the halls of residence
2. Isolation and characterization of microbial load of water samples from Africa hall, Unity hall, Republic hall, University hall, Queen Elizabeth hall and Independence hall.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Groundwater Quality

The exploitation of surface water has reduced due to the increase in surface water pollution and expensive nature of treatment hence resulting in an increase dependent on groundwater abstraction (Kortatsi, 2007). The use of groundwater has been developed in response to water shortage and service deficiency and often through private initiative but in a few cases, the use of groundwater has been embraced as part of planned urban water supply development (Allabo, 2016). The Ghana EPA is responsible for providing and ensuring that these laws and standards are achieved and that quality water is provided. The Ghana Water Company Limited (GWCL) currently operates 82 urban systems with an average daily output of 572,012 m³/day as against a daily demand of 1,049,306 m³/day (Addo, 2010). This shows that urban water supply by GWCL is insufficient for the urban community and there must be adjustments in policy implementation of urban water supply to ensure sustainable development as spelt out in Growth and Poverty Reduction Strategy II, New Partnership for African Development and the Millennium Development Goals, to which Ghana is signatory (Nyarko, 2008). An alternative such as the use of groundwater has been used for a period of time. Ghana's groundwater resources are under increasing pressure in response to threats of rapid population growth, coupled with the establishment of human settlements lacking proper water supply and sanitation services (Anim *et al.*, 2011).

The quality of groundwater is very important in evaluating its usefulness in various fields such as domestic, public water supply and agriculture, the assessment of the dissolved constituents thus become very important for safe drinking water. Most industries, schools, homes and agricultural sectors have adopted the groundwater supply due to its low cost and frequent supply. The original

chemical value of groundwater is good, however changes in chemical constituents can lead to severe problems when used. The University though considered a high priority area (for services such as water, electricity etc.) suffers intermittent supply of water. Due to the unreliability of water supply, all halls and many hostels, departments, colleges etc. have drilled boreholes to supplement the GWCL water with groundwater (Boakye, 2013).

2.2 Groundwater Contamination

The importance of groundwater quality in human health has recently attracted a great deal of interest (Pazand *et al.*, 2010). Research has shown a major link between water supply infrastructure, treatment operations, water quality, waterborne diseases and population health (Hrudey and Hrudey, 2005). Nonetheless, Ghana water management study in 1997 revealed that groundwater is also vulnerable to pollution due to anthropogenic and natural processes (Duodu, 2014). Major sources of pollution of groundwater are mostly unclear and often related to hygienic related activities like location of pit latrines in an area, landfills, disposal of wastes and leaching of agricultural chemicals into the soil. Pit latrines have been recognized as a key source of pollution of groundwater (wells) with human waste (Pritchard *et al.*, 2007). Water supplies contaminated with human and animal feces cause serious infections in humans. Coliform genera include both fecal (specifically present in intestine and feces of warm blooded animals) and non- fecal origin.

E. coli bacteria which belong to fecal coliform group, are harmless but few strains like *E. coli* 0157:H7 cause severe illness (Odonkor and Ampofo, 2013). Some ions dissolved in water and present in appropriate concentration are essential for human beings while higher concentration results in toxicity (Kumari *et al.*, 2018).

2.3 Water Supply and Quality

Water supply to the halls of residence on KNUST campus are obtained from two main sources, groundwater and from Ghana Water Company Limited (GWCL, Kumasi). Both are used concurrently in ensuring that there is constant distribution and flow of water. Notwithstanding, the quality of the water supplied should not be affected regardless of the source. Boreholes are scattered all over the university campus and the need therefore arises to assess the water supply capacity of KNUST and also to make a conscious effort to bring all the borehole water to a point where quality improvement can be done before its distribution to the whole university community (Boakye, 2013). Students and workers depend on the water for their various duties and not much concerns have been raised with regards to the quality of the water whether from ground or GWCL. Consumer satisfaction with drinking quality water is largely based on a judgment that the aesthetic quality of tap water is 'good', which usually means that it is colorless, free from suspended solids and has no unpleasant taste or odor (MWRWH, 2015). Feedbacks from consumers are important sources for the assessment of quality water since they make immediate use of the water.

2.4 Distribution and Storage System

Secondary water supply systems (SWSSs) refer to the in-building infrastructures (e.g., water tanks, pumps, pipes) that are used to store, pressurize and transport water from the distribution main to taps (Li *et al.*, 2018). Monitoring the integrity of the distribution and storage systems, and the quality of water supplied to consumers is necessary to confirm that drinking water quality is maintained (Patil *et.al*, 2012). Appropriate security needs to be put in place to prevent unauthorized access to, or interference with, water storages and reservoirs (WHO, 2008). Growth or persistence of biofilms should be minimized to reduce aesthetic problems, including unacceptable tastes, odors

and staining (Bartram and Howard, 2003). Storage of water in tanks and reservoirs are of importance in accessing quality water if distribution systems and pipe-lines are also treated and managed as expected thus preventing particulate matter and microorganisms from thriving and settling in the water.

2.5 Sources of Drinking Water

Groundwater is increasingly becoming the source of drinking water for inhabitants of both rural and urban settlements due to constant water shortage which has been hitting most parts of the country (Kyeremateng, 2014). Drinking water sources are varied, and include shallow and deep groundwater obtained through tube wells, small ponds with and without pond sand filters, harvested rainwater, bottled water and river water (Benneyworth *et al.*, 2016). The source of drinking water is rational and subjective and consumption may differ from an individual to the other.

2.6 Dirty Water

Dirty water refers to a water which contains pollutants both solid and liquid and can pose health related issues to people hence deemed unsafe and unclean for consumption. There are different contaminants in water which after consumption may be harmful to human beings, but making sure that the water is free from pathogens that are harmful to the body is of top priority. There several ways, these contaminants enter water to render it unsafe. Intake of dirty water usually causes disease commonly termed as “water borne diseases”. According to Ahmed (2010), skin and other infectious diseases can be acquired through the use of contaminated and dirty water. Studies have

shown that a number of socio-cultural practices including open air defecation, tethering of animals near human dwelling, proximity of animal fecal matter have found to lead to water contamination resulting in outbreak of diarrheal disease (Jayanthi and Soundararajan 2018). UNICEF (2017) reported from in their Child Survival Fact Sheet that, around 6,000 children die every day from diseases linked with lack of access to good quality drinking water, poor sanitation and hygiene

2.7 Water Treatment

Water received from their various sources; groundwater or GWCL to the students may be of the best quality, however, distribution and storage procedures may affect the quality of the water. Treatment of water from pipe lines, tanks and reservoirs is necessary in ensuring that quality water is distributed and made available for users. The enclosed nature of these tanks and storage reservoir ensures that atmospheric contamination of the water is inhibited nonetheless, these containers may harbor several microorganisms both pathogenic and non-pathogenic, chemical matter e.g. chlorine residuals, residuals from reactions on pipes, and other physical particulate matter such as sediments. Disinfection of the water is necessary to reduce if not eliminate most pathogenic and non-pathogenic organism which may cause diseases (Alaska, 2012). Because pathogens can be present in groundwater supplies, disinfection is very important and the EPA requires it for surface water as well (Pandey *et al.*, 2014). Disinfection treatment methods include chlorination, chlorine dioxide, chloramines, ozone, and ultraviolet light (Mensah, 2011; MWRWH, 2015). Disinfection is crucial to water system security, providing the “front line” of defense against biological contamination (Water Quality and Health Council, 2019).

2.8 Water Quality Parameters

Physicochemical and biological quality of water is important not only in the assessment of the degree of pollution but also in the choice of the best source and the treatment needed (Mensah, 2011). The parameters that were considered for this study are discussed below.

2.8.1 Potential of Hydrogen (pH)

The pH of a water is a measure of how acidic or alkaline (basic) the water usually on a scale of 0-14. Pure distilled water has a neutral pH measurement below 7 indicating that the solution is acidic. Measurement above 7 indicates that the reverse situation exists making the water alkaline. Though pH has both direct and indirect effect on the human health, all the biochemical reactions are sensitive to variation of pH (Gorde and Jadhav, 2013). For most reactions as well as for human beings, pH value near neutral or neutral is considered as good. WHO guidelines suggest that the optimum pH required in drinking water should be in the range 6.5-8.5 (WHO, 2008).

2.8.2 Temperature

Temperature affects the physical, chemical and biological processes in water bodies. The survival of microorganisms such as bacteria in water environments depends on the presence of nutrients and the water temperature (Edberg *et al.*, 2000). Variation in temperatures affect other parameters present in the water.

2.8.3 Electrical conductivity

Electrical conductivity is a measure of the ability of water to conduct an electrical current and is directly related to the total dissolved salt content of the water (Ogunde *et al.*, 2017). Since the electrical conductivity is a measure to the capacity of water to conduct electrical current, it is directly related to the concentration of salts dissolved in water, and therefore to the total dissolved solids (Tiakor, 2015). The more dissolved ions in water, the greater its electrical conductivity (Lorday, 2017). Electrical conductivity can be used as an indicator of water pollution since it measures the amount of dissolved solids (Strubbe, 2018). The World Health Organization permits a maximum limit of 300 μ S/cm (WHO, 2006). Conductivity is said to show a significant correlation with ten parameters such as temperature, pH value, alkalinity, total hardness, calcium, total solids, total dissolved solids, chemical oxygen demand, chloride and iron concentration of water bodies (Patil *et al.*, 2012).

2.8.4 Total Alkalinity

Alkalinity can also be defined as a measure of the presence of bicarbonate, carbonate or hydroxide constituents. High or low values of alkalinity affects other parameters. Other tests have proven that, excessive alkalinity may cause eye irritation in human and chlorosis in plants (Pawari and Gavande, 2015). The recommended range for drinking water is 30-400 ppm. High alkalinity (above 500 mg/l) is usually associated with high pH values, hardness and high dissolved solids (Lawson, 2011).

2.8.5 Chloride, (Cl⁻)

Chloride is one of the most important parameter in assessing the water quality and higher concentration of chloride indicates higher degree of organic pollution (Yogendra and Puttaiah, 2008). The maximum limit of chlorine in water according to the Ghana EPA is 250 mg/L with residual chlorine limit of about 0.2 mg/L (MWRWH, 2015). Chloride concentrations in excess of above 250 mg/L can give rise to detectable taste in water, but the threshold depends upon the associated cations (Lawson, 2011). The addition of chlorine to our drinking water has greatly reduced the risk of waterborne diseases. A major advantage of chlorine is that it has a residual disinfection effect, and it can ensure disinfection right up to the tap. No health- based guideline value is proposed for chloride in drinking-water. However, chloride concentrations in excess of about 250 mg/litre can give rise to detectable taste in water.

2.8.6 Fluoride (F⁻)

Naturally, fluoride are released into the environment through the weathering of rocks and through atmospheric emissions from volcanoes and seawater .The WHO recommended health based target for fluoride in drinking water is 1.5 mg/liter (MWRWH, 2015). Exposure to high concentration of fluoride during childhood, when teeth are developing, can result in mild dental fluorosis. There be tiny white streaks or specks in the enamel of the tooth. High intake of fluoride for a prolonged time can result in skeletal fluorosis. Symptoms include to joint pain, hindrances to movement, and high probability of some bone fractures. Skeletal fluorosis (with adverse changes in bone structure) may be observed when drinking-water contains 3–6 mg of fluoride per litre (Abu-zeid and Hatow, 2015). Crippling skeletal fluorosis usually develops only where drinking water contains over 10 mg of fluoride per liter (WHO, 2008). Groundwater from shallow hand dug wells was noted to

have much lower fluoride concentrations compared to groundwater from deep boreholes due to dilution by recent recharge (Kusi, 2015).

2.9 Microbiological Quality of Water

2.9.1 Microbial Load

Fecal pollution is one of the greatest source of microbial risk in underground water. Studies on hand dug wells and boreholes by Amin *et al.*, (2012), Obiri-Danso (2008), and Nyarko (2008) revealed high levels of total coliform, fecal coliform and *E. coli* in the water. Coliforms are natural fauna in soil and in the gut of humans and most animals. Their presence in water indicate contamination. The presence of coliform bacteria in well water may be as a result of surface water infiltration or seepage from a septic system (Obiri-Danso *et al.*, 2008).

2.9.2 Total and Fecal Coliform

Total coliforms are a group of bacteria usually found in the environment which do not to cause illness but their presence indicates a contamination. Fecal organisms have been also deemed as popular organisms to monitor in water especially groundwater because of its ability to be present in high numbers in the feces of humans and animals, and also because of its ability to be detected. High numbers of total coliform and detection of potential pathogens such as *Aeromonas* and *Pseudomonas* have been found in drinking water storage tanks across the world (Ahmed *et al.*, 2013) *E.coli* is found in the intestines of human as a harmless microorganism. Coliforms and *Escherichia coli* are widely used as indicators of microbial pollution in water though *E. coli* is specifically used as an indicator for fecal coliforms in drinking water (WHO, 2016).

The standard requirement for *E.coli* by WHO is 0 cfu/100ml (WHO, 2018). Although most strains of *E. coli* bacteria are harmless, certain strains, such as *E. coli* O157:H7 has been an important food and water borne pathogen that may cause illness, such as hemorrhagic diarrhea and hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS) which causes kidney failure in humans (Wasey and Salen, 2019). Improper treatment of groundwater before after and during storage may harbor many pathogens. Infants, the elderly, and those with compromised immune systems may be affected greatly by these pathogens and usually affect the skin, liver, lungs eyes and the nervous system. The effect may be fatal or at times chronic with respect to the degree of contamination. Effective treatment methods for microbial contamination include, permanent point-of-entry disinfection units, which can use chlorine, ozone, ultraviolet light (UV light), distillation (Mensah, 2011).

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Study Site

The University is situated in Kumasi, Ashanti Region in the south central of Ghana thus $6^{\circ}41''N$ and $1^{\circ}37''W$. It is approximately a 16km² campus, with six halls namely; Africa, Unity, University, Republic, Independence and Queen Elizabeth hall with other hostels as, GUSS, GRASAG, Hall 7, SRC and Brunei. Students and workers in the halls depend on two main sources of water for their various work purposes and other activities such as bathing, drinking, cooking, washing, etc. Poly-tanks and reservoirs are major storage facilities that channel water received from source to the students.

Figure 3.1 A map showing the various halls (Source:<https://www.researchgate.net>)

3.2 Study Design

There are a number of boreholes supplying the school with water. The study involved sampling of underground water from the six (6) halls of residence thus; Africa, Unity, Republic, Queen Elizabeth, Independence hall and University hall with sample codes of C01, C02, C03, C04, C05, C06 respectively. Water samples were collected from poly-tanks that served water into the bathrooms and kitchen, and those that served water for other purposes. The samples were taken early in the morning before sun rise.

3.3 Sample Collection

Water samples were collected from the borehole water outlets from six sites (halls of residence) thus; C01, C02, C03, C04, C05, C06. The samples were collected into a 500ml bottle and transported to the laboratory for analysis. Samples were taken once in triplicate from January to March 2019, and were kept in cold storage (to prolong the generation time of the microorganism) and then transported to the laboratory for analysis within 24 hours.

a. Water Filter

b. water pipeline

c. water reservoir

Plate 1: Some water distribution and storage equipment in the Halls

3.4 Determination of Physicochemical and Microbiological Parameters

3.4.1 The pH values

The pH values were determined using the PCD 650 meter, at the laboratory. The instrument has a probe with standard calibrations. The probe was inserted into about 10ml of the sample for about 5-15 minutes. Readings were taken and recorded after stabilization.

3.4.2 Temperature

The temperature of the water samples were taken on site at the time of collection. The probe of the thermometer was sterilized and inserted into the sample from the source. Temperature readings were taken and recorded.

3.4.3 Total Alkalinity

A 50ml of sample was measured into a conical flask followed by the addition of two drops of methyl orange indicator. The mixture was titrated against a standard 0.1M HCl(aq) until the first permanent pink color was seen usually at pH 4.5 (APHA, 1998). The calculation was done as follows;

$$\text{Alkalinity as CaCO}_3 \text{ (mg/l)} = A \times N \times 50,000 / T$$

Where

A = volume of acid used (ml)

T = volume of water sample (ml)

N = normality of standard acid used.

3.4.4 Conductivity

METLIER TOLEDO was used to measure the electrical conductivity of the water. 10ml of the water sample was poured into a beaker followed by the insertion of the probe into the measured sampled water. Measurements and readings were taken from the instrument in units of $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$.

3.4.5 Chloride (Cl^-)

A 100ml of the water sample was measured into a 250ml conical flask and three drops of Potassium dichromate indicator was added. The content in the conical flask was titrated against standardized silver nitrate solution, mixed by stirring to the end point which is indicated by a permanent red color. The volume of the titer was recorded and calculations were made.

Calculation

Chloride, $\text{mg}/\text{l} = \text{titer value} \times 10$

3.4.6 Fluoride (F^-)

SPADNS method

The SPADNS [(Sulphophenylazo) dihydroxynaphthalenedi-sulphonate] colorimetric method is based on the reaction between fluoride and a zirconium-dye lake. 50ml of the sample was measured into a conical flask followed by the addition of a 5.0 ml each of SPADNS solution and Zirconylacid reagent. The solution was then mixed and the absorbance read with initial reading at zero. Calibration curves were used to determine the fluoride concentration in the water sample. The

color produced is dependent on the fluoride concentration, thus, high fluoride concentrations produces lighter colors. Readings were recorded in (mg/l F-) in three significant figures.

3.5 Sample Preparation for Microbial Load

Nine (9) mls of distilled water was inoculated into test tubes. 5mls of prepared MacConkey broth was transferred into clean test tubes and sealed with cotton wool. Test tubes containing the broth were autoclaved and allowed to cool upon removal. The test tubes were labelled in a rack and serial dilutions were made.

3.6 Enumeration of Microorganisms

Total coliforms and fecal coliforms were enumerated by Most Probable Number (MPN) method and results were expressed as the Most Probable Number per 100ml (MPN 100ml⁻¹).

3.6.1 Total Coliforms

1ml of the sample was pipetted into test tube with 9ml distilled water and labelled 10⁻¹. 1ml of the 10⁻¹ solution was pipetted into all corresponding test tubes with label 10⁻¹ containing MacConkey broth on the rack. Another 1ml from the 10⁻¹ solution was pipetted into the next test tube labeled 10⁻² and method above was repeated for 10⁻³, 10⁻⁴, and 10⁻⁵ solutions. The rack was labelled and kept in an incubator for 24hours at 37°C. Test tubes which showed a yellow change in color indicates the presence of coliforms and recorded as positive whilst those that remained purple indicated the absence coliforms hence negative.

3.6.2 Fecal Coliforms

1ml of sample was pipetted into a sterilized test tube containing 9mls of distilled water and labelled 10^{-1} . 1ml of the 10^{-1} solution was pipetted into test tubes labelled 10^{-1} on the test rack containing 5mls of MacConkey broth. Another 1ml from the 10^{-1} solution was pipetted into a test tube with 9mls of distilled and labelled 10^{-2} . This procedure was repeated for 10^{-3} , 10^{-4} , and 10^{-5} solutions with their pipetted volumes into their corresponding test tubes on the triplicate rack. This rack was labelled “fecal” and also incubated for 24hours at 44°C . Test tubes whose color change from purple to yellow show the presence of fecal coliforms and those that show no difference in coloration account for the absence of fecal coliform

3.6.3 Enterococci

Enumeration of Enterococci was done on sterilized petri dishes by the inoculation of 1ml aliquots of their serially diluted sample. Plates was streaked and allowed to dry and an already prepared Slanetz and Bartley agar was added. Sample was incubated at 4hours at 37°C and later incubated at 44°C for 24hours. A Quebec Colony counter was used to count the number of colonies on the plates. Dark red somewhat brownish color colonies seen was counted and recorded for the presence of Enterococci.

3.6.4 *Escherichia coli*

All tubes showing the presence of fecal coliforms were tested for the presence of *E.coli* by transferring a drop of the liquid from the positive test tubes into 5ml test tube of tryptone water and incubated at 44°C at 24hours. A drop of Kovac's reagent was then be added to the tubes of tryptone water and all tubes that showed a red ring color development after gentle agitation will be recorded as positive for *E.coli*.

3.7. Gram Staining

Gram staining was done to separate the bacteria into two groups, which were Gram positive (appeared purple in color) and Gram negative (appeared pink in color).

3.8 Media Preparation

Many different media are used in culturing, isolating and identifying various microorganisms.

3.8.1 MacConkey Broth

MacConkey broth is a differential media and was used for the identification and enumeration of coliform. A 25g of the powder was added to 500ml of distilled water. 5ml of the broth was transferred into test tubes which were then sterilized by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes.

3.8.2 Plate Count Agar (PCA)

PCA is a non-selective media and supports total bacteria growth in samples. 8.75g of the PCA powder was added to a 500ml of distilled water and then heated. Media was sterilized, by autoclaving at 1210C for 15 minutes.

3.8.3 Nutrient Agar

Nutrient agar is used to grow a wide range of bacteria and fungi. It contains essential nutrients needed for the optimum growth of microorganisms. A 8.4g of nutrient agar powder was added to a 300ml of distilled water and heated to dissolve. This was then followed by autoclaving at 1210C for 15 minutes to sterilize it.

3.8.4 Tryptophan Broth

The broth was use for indole test to detect the presence of enteric bacteria in a sample. 7.5g of the powder was added to 500ml of distilled water and heated to completely dissolve. 5ml was then inoculated into test tubes and sterilized by autoclaving at 1210C for 15 minutes.

3.9 Sterilization Procedures and Materials

These are the various techniques and materials used in the laboratory to ensure that contamination of samples and equipment are reduced to the optimum levels. Some of these methods include chemical sterilization, autoclaving and flaming of equipment.

3.9.1 Chemical Sterilization

Alcohol was used to sterilize laboratory benches and working spaces of the laminar flow hood to prevent the contamination of samples during work. All glassware and equipment were washed with detergent.

3.9.2 Autoclaving

All culture media and aqueous solution, test tubes, pipette tips were autoclaved by subjecting them to steam of a temperature of 115°C for 60mins or 121°C for 20mins at 15psi pressure. This kills most bacteria spores that may be present.

3.9.3 Flaming

Inoculating loops and test tubes are passed through a Bunsen flame for few seconds to prevent contamination.

3.10 Statistical Analysis

The results obtained from the laboratory analysis and all other measurement were analyzed with Microsoft Excel 2017 and data obtained from Microsoft Excel was calculated by analysis of variance (ANOVA).

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 RESULTS

4.1 Physicochemical analysis of the sample water

The physicochemical parameter is essential for the analysis of water quality and to show variations from the set standards implies contamination. The table below shows the differences in variation of the various physicochemical parameters tested for the water samples collected from the various sites with sample codes C01, C02, C03, C04, C05, and C06. The physicochemical parameters tested include; pH, conductivity, alkalinity, chloride, fluoride, and temperature.

Table 4.1: Physicochemical parameters recorded for the various Halls

Parameters	Halls					
	C01	C02	C03	C04	C05	C06
pH	6.61	6.76	6.81	6.64	6.80	6.79
Electrical conductivity($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	167	179	152	161	172	168
Alkalinity(mg/l)	42	51	35	38	44	47
Fluoride(mg/L)	0.26	0.24	0.20	0.29	0.22	0.22
Chloride(mg/L)	0.29	0.31	0.35	0.37	0.32	0.32
Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	23.7	24.2	23.4	23.1	23.2	23.5

The pH values recorded from the water samples taken from the halls of residence ranged from 6.6-6.81. Site C01 recorded the least value followed by C04, C02, C06, C05 and the highest recorded at C03 with values of 6.61, 6.64, 6.76, 6.79, 6.80 and 6.81 respectively.

The values obtained for the electrical conductivity ranged between 179 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ – 152 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ with site C02 recording the highest and the least recorded at C03. Site C05 recorded the second highest followed by C06, C01 and C04, with values of 172 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, 168 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, 167 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, 161 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ respectively.

The highest value of Alkalinity was recorded at sample site C02 with a value of 51(mg/L) followed by site C06 with a value of 47(mg/L), site C05 recorded a value of 44(mg/L), C01 recording a value of 42(mg/L), site C04 with 38(mg/L) and C03 recording the least value of 35(mg/L).

Results obtained showed high fluoride levels at site C04 with value of 0.29(mg/L), followed by C01 with value of 0.26(mg/L), C02 with value of 0.24(mg/L), C06 and C05 with 0.22(mg/L) and C03 with value of 0.20(mg/L).

The chloride values ranged between 0.29 mg/l – 0.37 mg/l. The value recorded in C01 was 0.29mg/l, sample site C05 recorded a value of 0.32 mg/l, C04 with a value of 0.37mg/l, C02 recorded 0.31 mg/l, site C03 with a value of 0.35 mg/l and C06 recorded a chloride value of 0.32mg/l.

The temperature levels ranged from 23.7°C - 23.1°C as the highest recorded value of 23.7°C was attained at sample site C01 and the lowest of 23.1°C at site C04. Sample site C05 and C02 recorded values of 23.2°C, site C03 recorded a value of 23.4°C and C06 with a temperature value of 23.5°C.

4.2 Microbiological quality of sampled water at the various site

The microbial quality of water is one of the most important and essential quality parameter to consider. The microorganisms are determined by the presence of bacteria indicative of fecal (sewage) contamination, namely, total coliforms and fecal coliforms such as *Escherichia coli* (Mensah, 2011), and further tests on Enterococci. Table 4.2 shows the various bacteriological tests performed to obtain the microbial loads on samples collected from the various sampled site and the results obtained.

Table 4.2: Microbial load of the water samples from the Halls

Hall	Coliforms (MPN/100m)		Total viable count (CFU/mL)	Enterococci (CFU/mL)
	Total	Fecal		
C01	1.08×10^6	4.56×10^5	1.68×10^5	7.50×10^4
C02	2.53×10^6	7.87×10^5	5.57×10^5	1.14×10^4
C03	8.37×10^5	2.35×10^5	1.21×10^5	1.42×10^4
C04	1.11×10^6	1.37×10^5	5.51×10^4	3.36×10^3
C05	4.65×10^5	4.00×10^4	2.82×10^5	9.91×10^3
C06	2.48×10^6	1.85×10^5	1.05×10^6	2.82×10^4

4.3 Biochemical analysis of water samples

The table below shows the results recorded for the biochemical confirmatory test for the presence of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus sp.* The addition of the Kovac's reagent forms a red ring in the test tube giving a positive test indicating presence of *Escherichia coli*. The presence of effervescence also indicates the presence of *Staphylococcus sp* hence recorded as positive (Kusi-Appiah and Odiete, 2018).

Table 4.3: Biochemical test indicating the presence or absence of *E.coli* and *Staphylococcus sp*

Halls	Indole test	Catalase test
C01	Negative	Positive
C02	Positive	Positive
C03	Negative	Positive
C04	Negative	Positive
C05	Negative	Positive
C06	Negative	Positive

4.4 Physical and microscopic observations from prepared water samples obtained from the sampled codes

The physical characterization of the growth forms of the samples and the corresponding microscopic evaluation gives good information on the microorganisms that may be present and also the different stains picked up by the cell wall components of the microorganism. The table below shows the forms, elevation, margin and gram stain (positive or negative) picked up the bacteria present in the water sample.

Table 4.4: Description of bacteria and growth forms observed from the test conducted

Hall	Forms	Elevation	Margin	Bacteria	Gram stain
C01	Irregular	Flat	Undulate	Bacillus	+
	Circular	Raised	Entire	Staphylococcus	-
	Filamentous	Flat A	Lobate	Bacillus	-
C02	Rhizoid	Flat	Undulate	Bacillus	-
	Circular	Raised	Entire	Staphylococcus	+
	Irregular	Flat	Lobate	Bacillus	+
C03	Filamentous	Flat	Filiform	Diplococcus	+
	Circular	Convex	Entire	Staphylococcus	-
	Irregular	Flat	Undulate	Streptococcus	+
C04	Circular	Raised	Entire	Staphylococcus	-
	Filamentous	Flat	Lobate	Bacillus	+

C05	Filamentous	Flat	Filiform	Bacillus	+
	Circular	Convex	Lobate	Staphylococcus	+
C06	Circular	Raised	Entire	Staphylococcus	-
	Filamentous	Flat	Filiform	Bacillus	+
	Rhizoid	Raised	Filiform	Bacillus	-

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 DISCUSSION

5.1 Physicochemical properties of the water

The WHO being concerned with the delivery of safe and quality water set guidelines and standards that must be met in delivering water to individuals regardless of its use. pH, temperature, alkalinity, electrical conductivity, and other properties like odor taste color all affect the quality of water in one way or the other. A rise in some parameters in turn affect the other since most are dependent on one or the other.

5.1.1 pH Levels Obtained from Samples Collected

The pH values of the water samples were in the accepted range of 6.5 – 8.5 as recommended by WHO. Site C01 recorded the least value followed by C04, C02, C06, C05 and the highest recorded at C03 with values of 6.61, 6.64, 6.76, 6.79, 6.80 and 6.81 respectively. The results showed that the water was slightly acidic.

According to Boakye (2013), the pH values recorded for underground water (borehole) on KNUST campus ranged from 4.61 to 6.01 and were lower than the minimum GLV value (6.5) by WHO. The results obtained from our study was a little above that obtained by Boakye (2013) and this may be due to the varied time and seasonal factors within which the water samples were taken. The pH determines the content of toxic forms of ammonia to the non-hazardous form (Abubakari, 2016) and thus attention as be given to monitoring the pH . Acidity also affects the transport channels and infiltrate deadly trace metals into the water thus triggering difficulties like acid taste, fabric discoloration or blue-green blemishes in sinks and water system (USEPA, 2007).

5.1.2 Conductivity

The values obtained for the electrical conductivity ranged between 179 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ – 152 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ with C02 recording the highest and the least recorded at C03. C05 recorded the second highest followed by C06, C01, C04 with values of 172 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, 168 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, 167 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, 161 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ respectively. The results are in range with the WHO requirement of 300 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$.

The electrical conductivity of water depends on the water temperature; thus the higher the electrical conductivity, the higher the temperature of the water (EPA, 2012). This statement was confirmed by Sun *et al.*, (2018) as suggested that high temperatures may be a possible reason for increased electrical conductivity values. This trend was not seen all true for our results as inconsistent and varying conductivity values were recorded for the respective increase in temperature with the exception of site C02. The various levels of conductivity can be an indication of the presence of varying quantities of inorganic ions such as phosphate, nitrates and chloride (Lorday, 2017). Ogunde (2017) also stated that the ability to conduct electrical current was linked with total dissolved solids or salts thus a rise in dissolved ions increased conductivity. Conductivity, is not detrimental to man but changes in its levels affects the levels of other parameters and thus one of the important parameters to be checked always.

5.1.3 Alkalinity

The highest value of alkalinity was recorded at site C02 with a value of 51(mg/L) followed by C06 with a value of 47(mg/L), CO5 with 44(mg/L), C01 recording a value of 42(mg/L) C04 with 38(mg/L) and C03 recording the least value of 35(mg/L). There is no health guideline value for total alkalinity. Alkalinity is not considered detrimental to humans but is generally associated with

high pH values, water hardness and excess dissolved solids (WHO, 2006). High value of alkalinity gives undesirable taste to water (Wescoat, 2018). The levels obtained from the sampled water ranged from 35 – 51mg/L which were within the acceptable range. Varied values obtained are as a results of the variation in pH. Mensah (2011), stated that water with low alkalinity (less than 75 mg/l) are very sensitive to changes in pH; as alkalinity increases, the ability of water to resist pH increases, hardness also increases and this may be corrosive to metallic fittings. The results obtained therefore suggests that the water is safe for consumption and usage, but may have varying pH values over time.

5.1.4 Chloride

The chloride values ranged between 0.29 mg/l – 0.37 mg/l. The value recorded at site C01 was 0.29mg/l, C05 recorded a value of 0.32 mg/l, C04 with a value of 0.37mg/l, C02 recorded 0.31 mg/l, C03 with a value of 0.35 mg/l and site C03 recorded a chloride value of 0.32 mg/l. This results correlated with the test conducted by Boakye (2013), in his work on the assessing the water supply potential of boreholes on KNUST campus with site BH013 (corresponding sample code C04) recording the highest value although the chloride levels were in the recommended range.

Chloride is a broadly spread component in all kinds of rocks and soils and its levels can also be affected by infiltration of agrochemicals into the water table. Microscopic contamination is reflected by increased levels of chlorides as a result of carbon-based waste of animal and human origin (Kumar, 2010). Most people are able to smell and taste chlorine in water usually at levels well below 5 mg/l, and others at levels as low as 0.3 mg/l (WHO, 2011). Fazal-Ur-Rehman and Haider (2018) stated that high amounts of chloride can cause hardness making the water unfit for

drinking purposes because hardness cause health diseases in humans. The taste and odor of the water may be affected in water is not treated well and an increase in the chloride levels can be unfit for consumption. Fluoride can come from runoff and infiltration of chemical fertilizers in agricultural areas. Septic and sewage treatment system discharges in communities with fluoridated water supplies (Stewardship and Series, 2007). Results obtained showed high fluoride levels at C04 with value of 0.29(mg/L), followed by C01 0.26(mg/L), C02 with value of 0.24(mg/L), C06 and C05 with 0.22(mg/L) and C03 with value of 0.20(mg/L). When fluoride occurs in low levels of 0.8 to 1.0 mg/L it is of essence for fortifying of tooth surface. However, fluoride over 1.2 mg/L leads to tooth fluorosis (Avocefohoun *et al.*, 2017). The six samples analyzed recorded levels below the WHO standard limit of 1.5mg/L, the highest being 0.29mg/L and the least was 0.20mg/L. Fluoride in groundwater varies with varying rock constituents and does not usually exceed 10mg/L. The low results recorded may be as a results of less seepage of chemical fertilizers into the water table. Students and other users are not at risk of any health problems and have their teeth protected against tooth decay as they use the water supplied orally.

5.1.6 Temperature

The minimum daily temperature ranges from 20.1°C in January to 34°C in February (Boakye, 2013). The temperature levels of the water samples from the halls ranged from 23.7°C - 23.1°C as the highest recorded value of 23.7°C was attained in C01 and the lowest of 23.1°C in C04. C05 and C02 recorded a value of 23.2°C, C03 recorded a value of 23.4°C and C06 with a temperature value of 23.5°C. The temperature of the water recorded may be affected by the average weather conditions and the color of the poly-tanks which are black. Black colored objects are known to retain heat and this might have had influence of the temperature of the water at the time of

measurement. The temperature of the water is not harmful to the health of man but its influence on other parameters may alter their actual levels which may in turn alter their effect on end users.

The survival of microorganisms such as bacteria in water environments are dependent on the presence of nutrients and the water temperature (Edberg *et al.*, 2000). High water temperature enhances the growth of microorganisms and may increase problems related to taste, odor, color and corrosion (Oyem *et al.*, 2014). This high temperature after storage of water increased the number of fecal coliforms in storage tanks (Chalchisa *et al.*, 2017). Storage tank material and color can affect water temperatures in the tanks and placing the tank in a shaded location can reduce temperature (Cynthia and Schafer, 2012). Temperature affects the rate of chemical reactions in the water body (Olajire and Imeokparia 2001) and it plays an important role in the survival of microorganisms (Akuffo *et al.*, 2013).

5.2 Microbial Quality of the Water

Microbial quality of water means that no fecal and total coliform whatsoever ought to be identified in any potable water sources hence their presence indicates contamination thus the water is unsafe for consumption and attention needs to be given to it. Coliform bacteria are present in the environment and feces of all warm-blooded animals and humans. Coliform bacteria are unlikely to cause illness. However, their presence in drinking water indicates that disease-causing organisms (pathogens) could be in the water system. Sewage generated from homes in urban area is one of the water quality issues in the world (Water and Sanitation Programme and UNICEF, 2015).

5.2.1 Total and Fecal Coliform

The total coliform levels ranged from 2.53×10^6 MPN/100ml - 4.65×10^5 MPN/100ml with a p value of (0.751663) indicating that there was no significant difference in the total coliform levels recorded from the samples at the various sites.

The fecal coliform levels recorded ranged between 7.87×10^5 MPN/100ml - 4.00×10^4 MPN/100ml. The highest value of fecal contamination was recorded at C02 with a value of 7.87×10^5 MPN/100ml whilst the least contamination was recorded at C05 with a value of 4.00×10^4 MPN/100ml. There was no significant difference between the values recorded for the analysis of fecal coliforms with a p value of (0.288281).

Most of the filters which serve a function of blocking and reducing contamination of the water received were old and dirty as observed at site C04 and C02, others situated at unhygienic places as in C01 where the filter was located near a drainage system, and others were leaking as seen at site C06. Furthermore, some poly-tanks which stored water had broken covers, no covers and the dirty. Crows and other flying organisms may contaminated the water with feces and other materials. Long storage of the water may also affect the growth of these microorganism and this was confirmed by Akuffo *et al.*, (2013) stating that there are various reports on the re-growth of bacteria in water stored during a short or long time as recorded up to 250 cfu/100 ml of fecal coliform from water storage tanks found in Ghana. Although the UV light may play a role in killing the microorganisms, however, the mode of reproduction allows the microorganism to reproduce at a faster rate than may be killed.

The presence of the coliforms may also be as a results of the seepage of sewage into the water tables, heavy storm runoffs which may be contaminated with sewage. A study by Boakye (2013) indicated that the boreholes water examined on KNUST campus contained total coliform but

however, there were no levels of *E. coli*. According to Okoli *et al.*, (2005) the bacteriological analysis of borehole water utilized at the student hostels of the Federal University of Technology Owerri showed that the total coliform and total viable bacteria in most of the samples were too numerous to count, indicating that they were heavily contaminated with fecal matter. Thus, keeping the water storage tanks clean could improve the microbiological quality of stored water and reduce diarrheal and other waterborne diseases in communities. There is therefore an urgent need for proper treatment of water before distribution of underground water to be utilized (Ogunde *et al.*, 2017).

5.2.2 Total Viable Count / TVC

Samples tested for total viable count ranged between 1.05×10^6 CFU/mL - 5.51×10^4 CFU/mL. C04 recorded a value of 5.51×10^4 CFU/mL as the lowest, which was followed by C03, C01, C05, C02 and the highest value recorded at C06 with values of 1.21×10^5 CFU/mL, 1.68×10^5 CFU/mL, 2.82×10^5 CFU/mL, 5.57×10^5 CFU/mL, 1.05×10^6 CFU/mL. A *p* value of (0.568974) was obtained from the analysis hence there was no significant difference between the recorded values of the total viable count from the water samples at the various halls. Values recorded were high because the TVC media supports the growth of other forms of microbes aside bacteria (Joseph *et al.*, 2018)

5.2.3 Enterococci

The values obtained for enterococci was between C04 with a value of 3.36×10^3 CFU/mL and C01 with value of 7.50×10^4 CFU/mL with a *p* value of (0.397978) thus, there was no significant

difference of values for enterococci between the halls. In ascending order, CO5 recorded a value of 9.91×10^3 CFU/mL, C02 1.14×10^4 CFU/mL, C03 recording a value of 1.42×10^4 CFU/mL and C06 with a value of 2.82×10^4 CFU/mL. Enterococci are found in high concentrations in human feces, usually between $10^4 - 10^6$ bacteria per gram weight (Layton *et al.*, 2010) and this was in line with our results. The presence of these bacteria gives a clear indication of pollution. Thus there should be an urgent need to treat the water before distribution.

5.2.4 *Escherichia coli*

E. coli is the only member of the coliform group of bacteria which is found only in the intestines of mammals, including humans hence their presence indicates a fecal contamination thus a suspicion of a disease causing pathogen such as bacteria, parasites and viruses etc. present in the water. Although most strains of *E.coli* bacteria are harmless, certain strains, such as *E.coli* 0157:H7, may cause illness (Facts on Drinking Water). *E.coli* was tested positive at site C02. This could be as a result of spillage or leakage in the pipe lines that conveys the sewage to the main point of collection on campus, heavy storm-water runoff, leaching of animal manure etc. Again, this results may also be a false results. The various halls do not have independent latrines but all sewages are disposed at a particular location far from the halls. However, due to corrosion, mechanical and physical activities on the grounds, biological actions and changes in the water table structure, these fecal microorganisms could end up being transported to the underground water since both water distribution and sewage lines are all underground and any damage in one can affect the other.

All water samples recorded *Staphylococcus sp* as recorded in Table 4.3 and Table 4.4. This supports the claims of skin infection (Bouvet *et al.*, 2017) and presence of *Streptococcus* in site CO3 also supported the complaints on sore throat (Alexandre et al, 2017).

CHAPTER SIX

6.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

6.1 Conclusion

The physicochemical analysis carried out on the water samples were all good and in the acceptable range for consumption. However, the microbial aspect of the water was not within the limits specified by WHO. This could expose end users of the water from the halls of residence (C01, C02, C03, C04, C05 and C06) to serious health conditions. There is therefore a need and much attention should be given to the treatment of the underground water to the supplied halls against the presence of microorganisms to eliminate vulnerable diseases and illness.

6.2 Recommendation

Below are a few recommendations given which may help authorities to supply quality and good underground water to the students and workers on campus.

1. Poly-tanks and all water storage reservoirs should be well covered especially at site CO1, CO3 and CO4 to avoid contamination of the water.
2. Periodic test of the microbial quality should be conducted to ensure that safe water is supplied.
3. Filters at site C01, C03, C06 should be changed and all others that are non-functional.
4. Cleaning of the storage tanks with disinfectants like chlorine and not rinsing with water.

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APPENDICES

Plate 2: Color changes for the presence of the coliforms

Plate 3: Microscopic view of bacteria

Plate 4: Water storage container (poly-tank)

Plate 5: Enumeration of bacteria on PCA

APPENDIX 1A (ANOVA FOR TOTAL VIBLE COUNT)

HALL					
S	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	3501158565666 .667	5	700231713133. 333	.787	.569
Within Groups	2134336640800 0.000	24	889306933666. 667		
Total	2484452497366 6.668	29			

APPENDIX 1B Multiple Comparisons FOR TOTAL VIABLE COUNT

(I) PCA	(J) PCA	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1.00	2.00	113540.000	596424.994	1.000	-1730565.03	1957645.03
	3.00	-113440.000	596424.994	1.000	-1957545.03	1730665.03
	4.00	-876980.000	596424.994	.685	-2721085.03	967125.03
	5.00	-388000.000	596424.994	.986	-2232105.03	1456105.03
	6.00	46660.000	596424.994	1.000	-1797445.03	1890765.03
2.00	1.00	-113540.000	596424.994	1.000	-1957645.03	1730565.03
	3.00	-226980.000	596424.994	.999	-2071085.03	1617125.03
	4.00	-990520.000	596424.994	.569	-2834625.03	853585.03
	5.00	-501540.000	596424.994	.957	-2345645.03	1342565.03
3.00	6.00	-66880.000	596424.994	1.000	-1910985.03	1777225.03
	1.00	113440.000	596424.994	1.000	-1730665.03	1957545.03
	2.00	226980.000	596424.994	.999	-1617125.03	2071085.03
	4.00	-763540.000	596424.994	.793	-2607645.03	1080565.03
4.00	5.00	-274560.000	596424.994	.997	-2118665.03	1569545.03
	6.00	160100.000	596424.994	1.000	-1684005.03	2004205.03
	1.00	876980.000	596424.994	.685	-967125.03	2721085.03
	2.00	990520.000	596424.994	.569	-853585.03	2834625.03
5.00	3.00	763540.000	596424.994	.793	-1080565.03	2607645.03
	4.00	488980.000	596424.994	.961	-1355125.03	2333085.03
	6.00	923640.000	596424.994	.638	-920465.03	2767745.03

5.00	1.00	388000.000	596424.994	.986	-1456105.03	2232105.03
	2.00	501540.000	596424.994	.957	-1342565.03	2345645.03
	3.00	274560.000	596424.994	.997	-1569545.03	2118665.03
	4.00	-488980.000	596424.994	.961	-2333085.03	1355125.03
	6.00	434660.000	596424.994	.976	-1409445.03	2278765.03
6.00	1.00	-46660.000	596424.994	1.000	-1890765.03	1797445.03
	2.00	66880.000	596424.994	1.000	-1777225.03	1910985.03
	3.00	-160100.000	596424.994	1.000	-2004205.03	1684005.03
	4.00	-923640.000	596424.994	.638	-2767745.03	920465.03
	5.00	-434660.000	596424.994	.976	-2278765.03	1409445.03

APPENDIX 2A ANOVA FOR FECAL COLIFORM COUNTS

Hall

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	746193416666. 667	5	149238683333. 333	1.609	.288
Within Groups	556617500000. 000	6	927695833333.3 33		
Total	1302810916666 .667	11			

APPENDIX 2B Multiple Comparisons for Fecal Coliform Counts.

(I) fecal	(J) fecal	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	2	220500.000	304580.996	.971	-991685.69	1432685.69
	3	318500.000	304580.996	.886	-893685.69	1530685.69
	4	-331500.000	304580.996	.870	-1543685.69	880685.69
	5	271000.000	304580.996	.936	-941185.69	1483185.69
	6	416000.000	304580.996	.745	-796185.69	1628185.69

2	1	-220500.000	304580.996	.971	-1432685.69	991685.69
	3	98000.000	304580.996	.999	-1114185.69	1310185.69
	4	-552000.000	304580.996	.520	-1764185.69	660185.69
	5	50500.000	304580.996	1.000	-1161685.69	1262685.69
	6	195500.000	304580.996	.983	-1016685.69	1407685.69
3	1	-318500.000	304580.996	.886	-1530685.69	893685.69
	2	-98000.000	304580.996	.999	-1310185.69	1114185.69
	4	-650000.000	304580.996	.379	-1862185.69	562185.69
	5	-47500.000	304580.996	1.000	-1259685.69	1164685.69
	6	97500.000	304580.996	.999	-1114685.69	1309685.69
4	1	331500.000	304580.996	.870	-880685.69	1543685.69
	2	552000.000	304580.996	.520	-660185.69	1764185.69
	3	650000.000	304580.996	.379	-562185.69	1862185.69
	5	602500.000	304580.996	.444	-609685.69	1814685.69
	6	747500.000	304580.996	.269	-464685.69	1959685.69
5	1	-271000.000	304580.996	.936	-1483185.69	941185.69
	2	-50500.000	304580.996	1.000	-1262685.69	1161685.69
	3	47500.000	304580.996	1.000	-1164685.69	1259685.69
	4	-602500.000	304580.996	.444	-1814685.69	609685.69
	6	145000.000	304580.996	.995	-1067185.69	1357185.69
	6	1	-416000.000	304580.996	.745	-1628185.69
2		-195500.000	304580.996	.983	-1407685.69	1016685.69
3		-97500.000	304580.996	.999	-1309685.69	1114685.69
4		-747500.000	304580.996	.269	-1959685.69	464685.69
5		-145000.000	304580.996	.995	-1357185.69	1067185.69

APPENDIX 4A ANOVA FOR THE ENTEROCOCCI COUNT

HALLS

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	17495363986.6 67	5	3499072797.33 3	1.077	.398
Within Groups	77990314000.0 00	24	3249596416.66 7		
Total	95485677986.6 67	29			

APPENDIX 4B Multiple Comparisons for The Enterococci Count

Tukey HSD

(I) ENTEROCOCCI	(J) ENTERO COCCI	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	2	71674.000	36053.274	.378	-39800.24	183148.24
	3	63592.000	36053.274	.506	-47882.24	175066.24
	4	46760.000	36053.274	.784	-64714.24	158234.24
	5	65118.000	36053.274	.481	-46356.24	176592.24
	6	60768.000	36053.274	.554	-50706.24	172242.24
2	1	-71674.000	36053.274	.378	-183148.24	39800.24
	3	-8082.000	36053.274	1.000	-119556.24	103392.24
	4	-24914.000	36053.274	.981	-136388.24	86560.24
	5	-6556.000	36053.274	1.000	-118030.24	104918.24
	6	-10906.000	36053.274	1.000	-122380.24	100568.24
3	1	-63592.000	36053.274	.506	-175066.24	47882.24
	2	8082.000	36053.274	1.000	-103392.24	119556.24
	4	-16832.000	36053.274	.997	-128306.24	94642.24
	5	1526.000	36053.274	1.000	-109948.24	113000.24
	6	-2824.000	36053.274	1.000	-114298.24	108650.24
4	1	-46760.000	36053.274	.784	-158234.24	64714.24
	2	24914.000	36053.274	.981	-86560.24	136388.24
	3	16832.000	36053.274	.997	-94642.24	128306.24
	5	18358.000	36053.274	.995	-93116.24	129832.24
	6	14008.000	36053.274	.999	-97466.24	125482.24
5	1	-65118.000	36053.274	.481	-176592.24	46356.24
	2	6556.000	36053.274	1.000	-104918.24	118030.24
	3	-1526.000	36053.274	1.000	-113000.24	109948.24
	4	-18358.000	36053.274	.995	-129832.24	93116.24
	6	-4350.000	36053.274	1.000	-115824.24	107124.24
6	1	-60768.000	36053.274	.554	-172242.24	50706.24
	2	10906.000	36053.274	1.000	-100568.24	122380.24
	3	2824.000	36053.274	1.000	-108650.24	114298.24
	4	-14008.000	36053.274	.999	-125482.24	97466.24
	5	4350.000	36053.274	1.000	-107124.24	115824.24